

Guide for Expert Review of the GAI-SciTeach Focus Group Semi-Structured Interview Script - Task 2

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We ask you to critically analyse the **interview script** in light of **the study objectives** and the **defined constructs**, using the *feedback* form to record your observations.

Thank you for your availability and collaboration in the revision of this script.

1. Contextualization of the Study

1. Research question

What are science education stakeholders' perspectives about the integration of Generative Artificial Intelligence (GAI) in science education and in science teacher education?

Using the PICO framework (Hosseini et al., 2024):

- Population: stakeholders in science education (researchers and teacher educators, (future) teachers)
- Intervention/phenomenon: educational integration of GAI
- Context: science teaching, science teacher training

2. Research objectives

- To collect indicators of respondents' literacy in GAI in science education
- To assess the GAI perceived ease of use in science education and GAI tools learning curve
- To assess the perceived usefulness of GAI tools in enhancing science education
- To assess the perceived trust in GAI tools for content creation for science education and factors influencing it
- To assess perceptions on knowledge needed for GAI integration in science education
- To assess perceptions on the acceptance of GAI tools in science education
- To assess perceptions regarding GAI ethical issues in science education

3. Target audience

A *focus group* with each of the profiles (estimated 4-6 respondents) is planned:

- Education researchers/trainers of future science teachers;
- Future Science Teachers;
- Science teachers of the 3rd cycle of basic education / secondary education.

2. Materials for review

1. Construct definitions

GAI literacy: knowledge and understanding of what Generative Artificial Intelligence is, how it works, its applications, capabilities and limitations, including the respondent's ability to distinguish GAI-based tools and to choose the most appropriate ones for specific tasks.

Ease of use of GAI: The degree to which an individual believes that using GAI tools would be free of physical and mental exertion. It includes the perception of the clarity and simplicity of the interaction with the tools and the ease of acquiring the necessary skills for their effective use in teaching.

Usefulness of GAI: insight into whether the use of GAI tools can improve work performance, increase productivity, help to perform teaching tasks more effectively, and achieve higher quality outcomes in the context of science teaching and learning.

Trust in GAI: belief in the reliability, security, and accuracy of information and content generated by GAI tools. It includes confidence that tools meet expectations and consideration of risks to teacher and student privacy.

Knowledge for GAI integration: knowledge that science teachers need to effectively integrate GAI tools into their pedagogical practices. This involves the ability to properly combine specific disciplinary content (Content Knowledge), pedagogical strategies (Pedagogical Knowledge) and the functioning of GAI (Technological Knowledge) tools, also considering the capabilities and limitations of AI and its ethical implications. It includes the knowledge to use GAI for learning monitoring and adaptive *feedback*, for example.

Acceptance of GAI: intention and willingness to adopt and use GAI tools in the teaching and learning of science, as well as their support for their integration into the education system.

Ethical Issues of GAI use: perceptions and concerns about the ethical aspects related to the use of AGI in teaching, including the ability to teach students about ethics in GAI, safe and responsible behavior, protection of sensitive data (exams, grades, personal data), privacy, information security, and well-being when using these tools.

2. Practical instructions for the review, please:

- 1) Read each interview guide question: major and extension (defined as per Amado (2014)).
- 2) Evaluate the following criteria per question:
 - **Clarity:** The wording is understandable and appropriate to the target audience?
 - **Relevance:** The question effectively addresses the proposed construct (coherence of the constructs, objectives, and original formulation of the items in the baseline studies¹)? (Al-Abdullatif, 2024; Chiu et al., 2024)
- 3) Evaluate the following criteria by dimension:
 - **Comprehensiveness:** Does the dimension include enough questions to cover the construct? There are unnecessary redundancies?
- 4) The sequence of questions and dimensions seems logical and appropriate for a *focus group*?
- 5) Using the following form, which is part of the interview guide, indicate suggestions for reformulation or exclusion. Identify gaps or redundancies.

¹ The baseline studies were:

Al-Abdullatif, A. M. (2024). Modeling Teachers' Acceptance of Generative Artificial Intelligence Use in Higher Education: The Role of AI Literacy, Intelligent TPACK, and Perceived Trust. *Education Sciences*, 14(11), 1209. <https://doi.org/10.3390/EDUCSCI14111209>

Chiu, T. K. F., Ahmad, Z., & Çoban, M. (2024). Development and validation of teacher artificial intelligence (AI) competence self-efficacy (TAICS) scale. *Education and Information Technologies*, 30(5), 6667–6685. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S10639-024-13094-Z/FIGURES/1>

1. Focus group *interview guide* and form

The discussion group is organized into three sections: Introduction, Development (with the dimensions of analysis) and Closing.

Introduction to the *focus group*

Objectives	Information	Does it require reformulation? (Yes or No)	Qualitative comments (to be filled in only if you mentioned "yes" in the previous column; indicating lack of adequacy to the objectives, making suggestions, etc.)
Introducing the GAI-SciTeach project, the interviewer, and the objectives of the focus group	Project brief description and main expected results. Interviewer's name, affiliation, and area of work. We want to know your opinion on the use of generative artificial intelligence (GAI) in science education, namely with regard to GAI literacy, its ease of use, its usefulness, confidence in the content it generates (and factors that influence it), the knowledge that is necessary for its use, its acceptance and the ethical questions it raises.		
Thank the interviewees and recognize the value of their contributions			
Inform about GDPR and ethical procedures	With your permission, the discussion group will be audio-recorded and transcribed. Although the collection of personal data is not the objective, such information may be disclosed during the interview. In accordance with the confidentiality provisions of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), any personal data will be removed from the transcripts.		

Objectives	Information	Does it require reformulation? (Yes or No)	Qualitative comments (to be filled in only if you mentioned "yes" in the previous column; indicating lack of adequacy to the objectives, making suggestions, etc.)
	<p>You will receive anonymized transcripts for analysis and will have two weeks to review them and suggest any relevant corrections. The remaining data (non personal) will be used for research and may be shared in data repositories.</p> <p>Do you need further clarifications? Do you accept this procedure?</p>		

Development of the focus group

Dimension / Objective	Original questions (from the baseline studies)	Main questions	Probing questions	Evaluation (Likert scale: fill from 1 - nothing to 5 - totally)		Does it require reformulation? (Yes or No)	Qualitative comments (to be filled in only if you mentioned "yes" in the previous column, indicating lack of adequacy to the objectives, making suggestions, etc.)
				Clarity	Relevance		
GAI Literacy / To collect indicators of respondents' literacy in GAI in science education	I can explain what AI is [AIK3]. (Chiu et al. 2024)	1. Can you explain what Generative Artificial Intelligence is? <i>Pode explicar o que é a Inteligência Artificial Generativa?</i>	-	Clarity			
				Relevance			
			1a. Please define the concept as you understand it.	Clarity			
			<i>Por favor, defina o conceito como o entende.</i>	Relevance			
			1b. What examples would you use to illustrate what Generative Artificial Intelligence is ?	Clarity			
			<i>Que exemplos usaria para ilustrar o que é Inteligência Artificial Generativa?</i>	Relevance			
	I can distinguish whether a tool is AI-based or not. [AIK1] (Chiu et al. 2024)	2. How can people determine if new tools are based, or not, in Generative Artificial Intelligence ? <i>Como saber se uma ferramenta é baseada em Inteligência Artificial Generativa ou não?</i>	-	Clarity			
				Relevance			
			2a. Can you illustrate with an example?	Clarity			

			<i>Pode ilustrar com um exemplo?</i>	Relevance			
			2b. What characteristics indicate that a tool uses Generative Artificial Intelligence?	Clarity			
			<i>Que características indicam que uma ferramenta utiliza Inteligência Artificial Generativa?</i>	Relevance			
<p>I can use AI applications or products to improve my work efficiency. (AI-Abdullatif 2024)</p> <p>I can create content with AI. [AIK2] (Chiu et al. 2024)</p>	<p>3. How can people use GAI tools in science education for greater efficiency?</p> <p><i>Como usar ferramentas de Inteligência Artificial Generativa na educação em ciências tendo em vista uma maior eficiência?</i></p>	-	Clarity				
			Relevance				
		3a. Illustrate, by referring to concrete tasks and objectives (in science education) that can be accomplished/achieved more efficiently through the use of GAI tools.	Clarity				
		<i>Ilustre referindo tarefas concretas e objetivos (em educação de ciências) que podem ser realizadas/alcançados com maior eficiência através da utilização de ferramentas IAG.</i>	Relevance				

	<p>I know how to choose the right AI tools to effectively complete a task. [AIK4] (Chiu et al. 2024)</p> <p>I can evaluate the capabilities and limitations of an AI application or product after using it for a while. (AI-Abdullatif 2024)</p>	<p>4. How can people choose GAI tools that are adequate for carrying out a given task in science education ?</p> <p><i>Como escolher ferramentas de IAG adequadas à realização de uma dada tarefa em educação de ciências?</i></p>	-	Clarity			
				Relevance			
<p>Does the scope of the dimension require reformulation? Yes/No</p>	<p><i>Space for comments on whether the set of questions effectively covers the construct.</i></p>						

Dimension / Objective	Original questions (from the baseline studies)	Main questions	Probing questions	Evaluation (Likert scale: fill from 1 - nothing to 5 - totally)		Does it require reformulation? (Yes or No)	Qualitative comments (to be filled in only if you mentioned "yes" in the previous column, indicating lack of adequacy to the objectives, making suggestions, etc.)
				Clarity	Relevance		
Perceived Ease of Use of GAI tools / To assess the GAI perceived ease of use in science education and GAI tools learning curve	My interaction with GenAI tools is clear and simple. (Al-Abdullatif 2024)	5. How easy or difficult is it to use IAG tools and what factors influence this? <i>Em que medida é fácil ou difícil usar ferramentas de IAG e que fatores o influenciam?</i>	-	Clarity			
				Relevance			
			5a. Can you illustrate with an example? <i>Pode ilustrar com um exemplo?</i>	Clarity			
		Relevance					
	5b. What made it easy or difficult for you or for others you know? <i>O que tornou isso fácil ou difícil para si ou para outras pessoas que conhece?</i>	Clarity					
		Relevance					
	Learning how to use GenAI tools is easy for me. (Al-Abdullatif 2024) It is easy for me to become skillful in using GenAI tools. (Al-Abdullatif 2024)	6. How easy or difficult is it to learn to use GAI tools? <i>Em que medida é fácil ou difícil aprender a usar ferramentas IAG?</i>	-	Clarity			
				Relevance			
			6a. Can you describe your experience of building skills with GAI? <i>Pode descrever sua experiência de desenvolvimento de competências de utilização das ferramentas IAG?</i>	Clarity			
	Relevance						

			<p>6b. What kinds of support, experiences, or strategies have helped you feel more competent using them?</p> <p><i>Que tipos de apoio, experiências ou estratégias o ajudaram a sentir-se mais competente ao utilizar estas ferramentas?</i></p>	Clarity			
				Relevance			
	I find GenAI tools easy to use for my teaching. (AI-Abdullatif 2024)	7. How easy or how difficult is it to use GAI tools for science education?	-	Clarity			
				Relevance			
		<i>Em que medida é fácil ou difícil usar ferramentas de IAG na educação em ciências?</i>	7a. Can you illustrate with an example?	Clarity			
			<i>Pode ilustrar com um exemplo?</i>	Relevance			
Does the scope of the dimension require reformulation ? Yes/No	<i>Space for comments on whether the set of questions effectively covers the construct.</i>						

Dimension / Objective	Original questions (from the baseline studies)	Main questions	Probing questions	Evaluation (Likert scale: fill from 1 - nothing to 5 - totally)		Does it require reformulation? (Yes or No)	Qualitative comments (to be filled in only if you mentioned "yes" in the previous column, indicating lack of adequacy to the objectives, making suggestions, etc.)
				Clarity	Relevance		
Perceived Usefulness / To assess the perceived usefulness of GAI tools in enhancing science education	I find GenAI tools useful for performing my teaching duties. (AI-Abdullatif 2024) Using GenAI tools increases my chances of achieving high job performance. (AI-Abdullatif 2024) Using GenAI tools helps me accomplish my teaching tasks effortlessly. (AI-Abdullatif 2024) Using GenAI tools increases my productivity. (AI-Abdullatif 2024)	8. How useful can GAI tools be in science education?? <i>Quão útil podem ser as ferramentas IAG na educação em ciências?</i>	-	Clarity			
				Relevance			
			8a. Can you illustrate with an example? <i>Pode ilustrar com um exemplo?</i>	Clarity			
				Relevance			
			8b. Can you elaborate on its usefulness for achieving higher quality results/outputs or to reduce the time needed for a certain task? <i>Pode explicar a sua eventual utilidade para alcançar uma maior qualidade dos resultados na educação em ciência?</i>	Clarity			
				Relevance			
			8c. How does it affect the effort required to complete a task? <i>Como pode (ou não) impactar o esforço necessário para completar uma tarefa? E.g., uma ferramenta que permite criar diagramas, imagens rotuladas ou recursos semelhantes, seria útil para os professores e/ou para os alunos? Porquê ou por que não?</i>	Clarity			
				Relevance			
Does the scope of the dimension require	<i>Space for comments on whether the set of questions effectively covers the construct.</i>						

reformulation? Yes/No	
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Dimension / Objective	Original questions (from the baseline studies)	Main questions	Probing questions	Evaluation (Likert scale: fill from 1 - nothing to 5 - totally)		Does it require reformulation? (Yes or No)	Qualitative comments (to be filled in only if you mentioned "yes" in the previous column, indicating lack of adequacy to the objectives, making suggestions, etc.)
				Clarity	Relevance		
GAI Perceived Trust / To assess the perceived trust in GAI tools for content creation for science education and factors influencing it	I will use the GenAI tools if I feel that the content is trustworthy. (Al-Abdullatif 2024) I will use the GenAI tools if I feel that these tools provide reliable information. (Al-Abdullatif 2024) I will use the GenAI tools if I feel that these tools meet my expectations. (Al-Abdullatif 2024)	9. What factors affect people's trust and will to use GAI tools for content creation? <i>Que fatores afetam a confiança e a vontade das pessoas de usar as ferramentas de IAG para a criação de conteúdo?</i>	-	Clarity			
			Relevance				
			9a. Do you trust it? In what aspects do you (not) trust it? Can you illustrate with examples? <i>Confia nestas ferramentas? Em que aspetos (não) confia? Pode ilustrar com exemplos?</i>	Clarity			
			Relevance				
			9b. How does knowing whether something is created by GA affects your opinion or the way you use it? Why? <i>Em que medida saber que algo é gerado por IAG afeta a sua opinião ou a forma como o usa? Porquê?</i>	Clarity			
			Relevance				

	I will use the GenAI tools if I feel that these tools are secure. (Al-Abdullatif 2024) I will use the GenAI tools if the data use poses no risks to teacher and learner privacy. (Al-Abdullatif 2024)	10. How does users' sense of security and data privacy—or lack thereof—influence their willingness to use GAI tools? <i>De que forma a percepção de segurança e privacidade dos dados por parte dos utilizadores — ou a falta dela — influencia a sua disposição para usar ferramentas de IAG?</i>	-	Clarity			
				Relevance			
			10a. What kinds of security concerns come to mind about these tools? Que tipo de preocupações de segurança lhe ocorrem acerca da utilização das ferramentas de Inteligência Artificial Generativa?	Clarity			
				Relevance			
			10b. How do you weigh the potential benefits of GAI tools against the possible risks (e.g., privacy issues)? <i>Como avalia os benefícios potenciais das ferramentas de IAG em relação aos possíveis riscos?</i>	Clarity			
				Relevance			

Does the scope of the dimension require reformulation?
Yes/No

Space for comments on whether the set of questions effectively covers the construct.

Dimension / Objective	Original questions (from the baseline studies)	Main questions	Probing questions	Evaluation (Likert scale: fill from 1 - nothing to 5 - totally)		Does it require reformulation? (Yes or No)	Qualitative comments (to be filled in only if you mentioned "yes" in the previous column, indicating lack of adequacy to the objectives, making suggestions, etc.)	
				Clarity	Relevance			
Intelligent TPACK / To assess perceptions on knowledge needed for GAI integration in science education	I can teach lessons that appropriately combine my teaching content, GenAI tools, and teaching strategies. (Al-Abdullatif 2024) I can choose an AI tool to use in my classroom that enhances what I teach, how I teach, and what students learn. [AIP1] (Chiu et al. 2024) I can choose an AI tool that enhances my teaching subject content for a lesson. [AIP2] (Chiu et al. 2024) I can teach lessons that appropriately combine my teaching subject, AI tools, and Teaching approaches. [AIP3] (Chiu et al. 2024)	11. What type of knowledge science teachers need to appropriately combine their teaching content, GAI tools, and teaching strategies to promote learning? <i>Que tipo de conhecimento os professores de ciências precisam para combinar adequadamente o conteúdo de ensino, ferramentas IAG e estratégias de ensino, para promover a aprendizagem?</i>	-	Clarity				
				Relevance				
				11a. Can you illustrate with an example?	Clarity			
				<i>Pode ilustrar com um exemplo?</i>	Relevance			
				11b. What teaching content is suited to be addressed in teaching strategies that include GAI?	Clarity			
				<i>Que conteúdo de ensino é adequado para ser abordado em</i>	Relevance			

			<i>estratégias de ensino que incluem IAG?</i>				
			11c. What GAI tools can be successfully used in science educations? <i>Que ferramentas de IAG podem ser usadas com sucesso na educação em ciências?</i>	Clarity			
				Relevance			
			11d. What teaching strategies can be explored in this context? <i>Que estratégias de ensino podem ser exploradas neste contexto?</i>	Clarity			
				Relevance			
	<p>In teaching my field, I know how to use different GenAI tools for adaptive and real-time feedback. (Al-Abdullatif 2024)</p> <p>In teaching my field, I know how to use different GenAI tools for personalized learning. (Al-Abdullatif 2024)</p> <p>I can select various GenAI tools to monitor students' learning in my teaching process. (Al-Abdullatif 2024)</p> <p>I can use AI tool to foster assessment for learning. [AIA1] (Chiu et al. 2024)</p>	<p>12. What type of knowledge science teachers need to appropriately use GAI tools to foster assessment for learning and to assess processes?</p> <p><i>Que tipo de conhecimento os professores de ciências precisam para usar adequadamente as ferramentas de IAG para promover a avaliação da</i></p>	-	Clarity			
				Relevance			

	<p>I can design an assessment approach to improve student learning in an AI-based environment (e.g., learning with ChatGPT). [AIA2] (Chiu et al. 2024)</p> <p>I can choose an AI tool to foster student self-assessment. [AIA4] (Chiu et al. 2024)</p>	<p><i>aprendizagem e avaliar processos?</i></p>	<p>12a. E.g., what GAI tools support monitoring students' learning, to provide real-time feedback and personalized learning to students, or to foster students' self-assessment?</p> <p><i>E.g., Que ferramentas de GAI apoiam a monitorização da aprendizagem dos alunos, para fornecer feedback em tempo real e aprendizagem personalizada aos alunos, ou para fomentar a autoavaliação dos alunos?</i></p>	Clarity				
				Relevance				
		<p>In teaching my field, I know how to use different GenAI tools for generate quiz and assessments. (Al-Abdullatif 2024)</p>	<p>13. What type of knowledge science teachers need to use GAI tools of teaching and learning to evaluate students' learning?</p>	-	Clarity			

		<i>Que tipo de conhecimento os professores de ciências precisam para usar as ferramentas de IAG de ensino e aprendizagem para avaliar a aprendizagem dos alunos?</i>		Relevance			
			13a. What GAI tools can work well in this area (e.g., to generate quizzes)?	Clarity			
			<i>Que ferramentas de IAG podem funcionar bem nesta área (por exemplo, para gerar questionários)?</i>	Relevance			
			13b. What challenges or limitations can happen when using GAI tools this way?	Clarity			
			<i>Que desafios ou limitações podem surgir ao usar ferramentas de IAG desta forma?</i>	Relevance			
Does the scope of the dimension require reformulation? Yes/No	<i>Space for comments on whether the set of questions effectively covers the construct.</i>						

Dimension / Objective	Original questions (from the baseline studies)	Main questions	Probing questions	Evaluation (Likert scale: fill from 1 - nothing to 5 - totally)		Does it require reformulation? (Yes or No)	Qualitative comments (to be filled in only if you mentioned "yes" in the previous column, indicating lack of adequacy to the objectives, making suggestions, etc.)
GAI Acceptance / To assess perceptions on the acceptance of GAI tools in science education	I look forward to use GenAI tools in my teaching. (Al-Abdullatif 2024) I intend to use GenAI tools in my future teaching. (Al-Abdullatif 2024) I plan to use GenAI tools in my future teaching. (Al-Abdullatif 2024) I support the adoption of GenAI tools in higher education. (Al-Abdullatif 2024)	14. What are the perspectives among science teachers and students, parents and school heads about integrating GAI in teaching practice? <i>Quais são as perspetivas entre professores e alunos de ciências, pais e diretores escolares sobre a integração da IAG na prática docente?</i>		Clarity			
				Relevance			
			14a. E.g., how important is it to integrate GAI in science teaching and why? <i>E.g., qual a importância de integrar IAG no ensino das ciências e porquê?</i>	Clarity			
				Relevance			
			14b. Can you illustrate with examples of situations when people revealed reservations or excitement about using these tools in science education? <i>Pode ilustrar com exemplos de situações em que as pessoas revelaram reservas ou entusiasmo</i>	Clarity			
				Relevance			

			<p><i>em usar essas ferramentas na educação de ciências?</i></p>				
			<p>14c. Should GAI adoption in science education be supported? How? Why?</p>	Clarity			
			<p><i>A adoção das IAG no ensino de ciências deve ser apoiada? Como? Porquê?</i></p>	Relevance			
<p>Does the scope of the dimension require reformulation? Yes/No</p>	<p><i>Space for comments on whether the set of questions effectively covers the construct.</i></p>						

Dimension / Objective	Original questions (from the baseline studies)	Main questions	Probing questions	Evaluation (Likert scale: fill from 1 - nothing to 5 - totally)		Does it require reformulation? (Yes or No)	Qualitative comments (to be filled in only if you mentioned "yes" in the previous column, indicating lack of adequacy to the objectives, making suggestions, etc.)
GAI Ethics / To assess perceptions regarding GAI ethical issues in science education	I can teach students ethics [AIE1] (Chiu et al. 2024) I teach students how to behave safely and responsibly when learning with AI tools. [AIE4] (Chiu et al. 2024) I can ensure my health and well-being while using AI tools. [AIE3] (Chiu et al. 2024)	15. What topics do you consider important to include when discussing GAI ethics with students and colleagues? <i>Que tópicos considera importantes incluir ao discutir a ética no uso da IAG com os alunos e com colegas?</i>	-	Clarity			
				Relevance			
			15a. What kind of guidelines or expectations should be set for responsible and safe GAI use, e.g., to ensure people's health and well-being while using it? <i>Que tipo de diretrizes ou expectativas devem ser estabelecidas para o uso responsável e seguro da IAG, por exemplo, para garantir a saúde e o bem-estar das pessoas ao usá-lo?</i>	Clarity			
		Relevance					

	<p>I always comply with ethical principles when using AI applications or products. (AI-Abdullatif 2024)</p> <p>I am alert to privacy and information security issues when using AI applications or products. (AI-Abdullatif 2024)</p> <p>I can protect sensitive content from AI tools (e.g., exams, students' grades and personal data). [AIE2] (Chiu et al. 2024)</p>	<p>16. What kinds of privacy and information security issues are important to consider when using GAI tools in science education?</p> <p><i>Que tipo de questões de privacidade e segurança da informação são importantes considerar ao usar ferramentas de IAG na educação em ciências?</i></p>	-	Clarity			
				Relevance			
			16a. What steps should be taken to ensure that sensitive materials — like exams, grades, or student data — are protected when using AI tools? <p><i>Que medidas devem ser tomadas para garantir que materiais confidenciais, como exames, notas ou dados de alunos, sejam protegidos ao usar ferramentas de IAG?</i></p>	Clarity			
				Relevance			
Does the scope of the dimension require reformulation? Yes/No	Space for comments on whether the set of questions effectively covers the construct.						

Closing of the *focus group*

Objectives	Information	Does it require reformulation? (Yes or No)	Qualitative comments (to be filled in only if you mentioned "yes" in the previous column; indicating lack of adequacy to the objectives, making suggestions, etc.)
Collect potential unanticipated contributions	<p>Are there other training needs in GAI, enabling factors, barriers or other aspects that you wish to address?</p> <p><i>Deseja abordar outras necessidades de formação em IAG, fatores favoráveis, barreiras ou outros aspetos?</i></p>		
Thank respondents for participating and recognize the value of their contribution			

Other Suggestions – point 4 of the "Practical Instructions for Revision"

(Space to comment on the sequence of questions and dimensions and any other suggestions or observations that you consider pertinent. Optional)

Thank you once again for your time and your contribution to the quality of this research instrument.

1. References

- Al-Abdullatif, A. M. (2024). Modeling Teachers' Acceptance of Generative Artificial Intelligence Use in Higher Education: The Role of AI Literacy, Intelligent TPACK, and Perceived Trust. *Education Sciences*, 14(11), 1209. <https://doi.org/10.3390/EDUCSCI14111209>
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